

Review

The role of redox-sensitive cysteines in multi sub-unit transcription factors

Byron Baron^{1,2*}

¹Department of Anatomy and Cell Biology, Faculty of Medicine and Surgery, University of Malta, Msida, Malta.

²Department of Biochemistry and Functional Proteomics, Yamaguchi University Graduate School of Medicine, Ube, Japan.

* Corresponding author, Email: angenlabs@gmail.com

Abstract

In response to oxidative stress, cells activate numerous processes and initiate the expression of genes via redox-sensitive transcription factors including the multi sub-unit transcription factors nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), activator protein 1 (AP-1), Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF1 α), Polyoma virus enhancer-binding protein 2 (PEBP2), cAMP-responsive element-binding protein (CREB), Nuclear Factor I/CCAAT Transcription Factor (NFI/CTF), Nuclear transcription factor Y (NF-Y) and E4 Transcription Factor 1 - 60kDa (E4TF1-60). Thioredoxin plays a critical role in this by directly or indirectly (via redox factor 1) reducing redox-sensitive cysteine residues in these transcription factors to modify their tertiary structure, sub-cellular localisation, protein-protein interactions or DNA-binding affinity. The identity of the redox-sensitive cysteine in E4TF1-60 has not been investigated so far. Determining which cysteines are redox-sensitive within the E4TF1-60 protein sequence together with elucidation of which property is modified will help to better understand the mechanism by which the E4TF1 complex is involved in regulating the cellular oxidative stress response.

Keywords

Epigenetics, post-translational modifications, oxidative stress, cysteine redox, transcription factors

Highlights

1. Oxidative stress triggers transcription factors activity through cysteine redox
2. Thioredoxin and Ref-1 are key elements in the redox of cysteines in transcription factors
3. Stress-induced multi sub-unit transcription factors contain one or more redox-sensitive cysteines
4. Cystein redox alters transcription factor DNA-binding, protein-interaction, localisation and transactivation
5. The transcription factor E4TF1-60 has 4 putative redox-sensitive cysteines at the C-terminus

Oxidative stress

Oxidative stress occurs when the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), superoxide (O₂⁻), the peroxy radical (ROO \cdot) and the hydroxyl radical (OH \cdot) is greater than the cell's antioxidant capacity. This capacity is derived from the balance between a number of molecular pairs having a reduced and oxidised component including thioredoxin (Txn), glutathione (GSH), nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP). These redox pairs in turn affect the redox-dependent state and consequently, the function of a number of transcription factors (Figure 1).

Oxidative stress can result either due to endogenous ROS production such as from metabolic processes, mainly oxidative phosphorylation in mitochondria or exogenous

stressors such as ionising radiation or ultraviolet radiation. High levels of ROS deregulate cellular defence systems and cause damage to macromolecules, genomic instability and disease including cancer [1-3].

In fact, oxidative stress has been reported to be involved in all three stages of cancer i.e. initiation, promotion, and progression, as ROS can cause gene mutations, genomic instability and structural alterations to DNA as well as contribute towards altering transcription and signal transduction pathways (leading to abnormal gene expression), which could result in decreased apoptosis and increased cell proliferation [4-6].

The role of thioredoxin in redox systems

Txn is a 12kDa ubiquitous protein that has a redox-active disulphide/dithiol made up of Cys-32 and Cys-35(-Cys-Gly-Pro-Cys-) within its conserved active site sequence, which confer its reducing activity [7-9]. It fulfils a multitude of biochemical functions including antioxidant defense through repair of oxidatively damaged proteins, refolding of mispaired disulfide-containing proteins (via Cys-31 in the active site) e.g. RNase A, involvement in synthesis of deoxyribonucleotides (via ribonucleotide reductase), electron donor to peroxiredoxins and modulation of immune cell function. Of major relevance is that reduced Txn acts on the cysteine residues of transcription factors to modulate their

Figure 1 Summary of the biochemistry activated by oxidative-stress and its effect on transcription regulation of multi sub-unit redox-sensitive transcription factors.

protein-protein or protein-DNA interactions [10,11]. Txn translocates from the cytoplasm into the nucleus following oxidative stress, to regulate gene expression by directly interacting with transcription factors or indirectly through the redox factor 1/AP endonucleases 1 (Ref-1/APE1) [12,13].

The importance of Txn-dependent redox control can be seen by its over-expression in cancers attempting to survive stress and escape therapy-induced death. Increased TXN1 mRNA and protein expression have been reported for breast cancer, thyroid cancer, prostate cancer, colorectal cancer, and malignant melanoma as well as aggressive invasive mammary carcinomas and advanced malignant melanomas compared with less aggressive tumours [14]. Increased TXN1 levels have been linked to the development of chemoresistance [15,16] and reduced patient survival, as observed in non-small-cell lung cancer [17] and colorectal cancer [18]. This link to aggressive phenotypes exhibiting a lower apoptosis rate, a higher growth potential, and an elevated invasion capacity, implicates the

thioredoxin system in the different stages of tumour development [14].

Ref-1 is a bifunctional enzyme, acting both as a DNA-repair enzyme and as a redox modulator. The DNA-repair function on apyrimidinic/apurinic nucleotides (via the base excision repair pathway) is through the C-terminal region, while the redox function is carried out by the redox regulatory domain at the N-terminal region, which also harbours a nuclear localisation sequence. The redox regulatory domain is characterised by 2 critical cysteines, Cys-65 and Cys-93 [19,20], which are important in the reduction of a cysteine residue within the DNA-binding motif and thus functional activation of transcription factors such as activator protein-1 (AP-1) (Fos and Jun), nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), p53, activating transcription factor/cAMP-response element-binding protein (ATF/ CREB), hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF)-1 α , HIF-like factor (HLF) and PAX5 [21-26]. Ref-1 can bind to and be regenerated by Txn [27,12].

For the same reasons as Txn, elevated Ref-1 expression has been observed in tumours such as cervical, leiomyoma, leiomyosarcoma, epithelial

ovarian cancers, pediatric rhabdomyosarcomas, prostate and germ cell, compared to normal tissues [22,28,29]. The localisation of Ref-1 is tumour-specific. Exclusively nuclear localisation of Ref-1 was observed in the progression of ovarian carcinomas [30], while epithelial ovarian cancers displayed both nuclear and cytoplasmic localisation, but with predominantly cytoplasmic localisation [31]. The expression levels of Ref-1 have also been linked to chemo- and radio-therapy resistance in cervical cancer [32], testicular cancer of various histologies [33] and pancreatic cancer [34].

Modulation of transcription factor function by thioredoxin and Ref-1

In response to oxidative stress, cells activate numerous processes such as the breakdown of reactive species and the repair of damaged macromolecules, particularly DNA. The notable feature is that the expression of redox-induced genes is regulated via transcription factors whose structure, sub-cellular localisation, or DNA-binding affinity is directly or indirectly regulated by the level of oxidative stress.

The physical impact of oxidative stress on the activity of redox-sensitive transcription factors, is the oxidation or reduction of one or more cysteines within the DNA-binding or transactivation domain in either a direct Txn (Ref-1 independent) or an indirect Txn (Ref-1 dependent) manner [35-37] (Figure 2). The primary target of redox regulation is the sulfhydryl group (RSH) on cysteine residues, which can be readily oxidised to form a disulfide bond (RSSR), sulfenic acid (RSOH), sulfinic acid (RSO₂H) or sulfonic acid (RSO₃H). For example, reduction of specific cysteine residues in c-Jun (Cys-272), c-Fos (Cys-154), and the p50 sub-unit of NF-κB (Cys-62) is required to activate the DNA-binding activity of these transcription factors [27,38-40]. Such redox-sensitive cysteine residues are commonly surrounded by basic amino acid residues, which enhance their reactivity as is observed in c-Fos, c-Jun and NF-κB [41].

The modulation of redox-regulation becomes more intricate when the transcription factor has either multiple redox-sensitive cysteines available e.g. p53 [42] or is composed of sub-units which respond differently to regulation through redox-sensitive cysteines e.g. Nuclear Factor-κB (NF-κB) [43], Activator Protein 1 (AP-1) [27,44], Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF1α) [45], Nuclear Factor I/CCAAT Transcription Factor (NFI/CTF) [46], Nuclear transcription factor Y (NF-Y) [47], Polyoma virus enhancer-binding protein 2 (PEBP2) [48], cAMP-responsive element-binding protein (CREB) [49], Heat Shock Factor 1 (HSF1) [50,51] and E4 Transcription Factor 1 (E4TF1) [52]. In such a complex setting, aberrant redox regulation easily leads to breakdown of this control system, with the major consequence of

aberrant reduction of these transcription factors being carcinogenesis.

Figure 2 The process involved in the transfer of protons in the thioredoxin system via A) direct-Txn action (Ref-1 independent) or B) indirect-Txn action (Ref-1 dependent) onto cysteine residues within the DNA-binding domains of redox-sensitive transcription factors (labelled in the figure as 'TF'). The reduction of specific cysteine residues activates or increases DNA-binding activity, thus initiating or enhancing transcription.

Nuclear Factor-κB (NF-κB)

One of the best studied multi sub-unit redox-sensitive transcription factors is NF-κB due to its high sensitivity to oxidative stress [53]. NF-κB consists of two sub-units, p50 and p65, which contain a Rel-homology domain (RHD), so-called for the high degree of homology to the proto-oncogene Rel [38,54]. The oxidised p50 sub-unit forms dimers through a disulphide bond involving Cys-62, which is located in the RHD [43]. The replacement of Cys-62 with serine results in decreased levels of DNA-binding activity. Rel is similarly regulated by redox through a corresponding cysteine residue in a manner similar to the regulation of p50 [55].

NF-κB is sequestered in the cytoplasm by Inhibitors of κB (IκBs) masking the NF-κB nuclear localisation until the IκBs are degraded in response to pro-inflammatory cytokines and NF-κB translocates

to the nucleus. NF- κ B binds to DNA motifs having the consensus sequence 5'-GGGA/GNNT/CT/CCC-3' (where N is any base) to activate or enhance the transcriptional activity of genes that mediate the immune response, stress response, cell growth and cell survival [53].

NF- κ B is known to regulate several genes involved in cell transformation, proliferation, and angiogenesis [56] and the constitutive expression of activated NF- κ B has been reported in colon, breast, pancreas, and squamous cell carcinomas [57].

Activator Protein 1 (AP-1)

Another well-studied redox-responsive transcription factor is AP-1, which is a complex made up of members from the Jun (c-Jun, JunB, and JunD) and Fos (c-Fos, Fra-1, Fra-2, and FosB) oncogenic protein families [58]. These sub-units of AP-1 contain the basic-leucine zipper (bZIP) motif, at the C-terminal region, which mediates dimerisation of Jun-Jun homodimers or Jun-Fos heterodimers through the leucine zipper and DNA-binding via the basic region. These bind to the consensus sequence 5'-TGAG/CTCA-3' present in the promoter region of genes implicated in cell proliferation, differentiation, invasion, inflammation, and stress response [59,60]. AP-1 activates gene expression in response to various influences, including growth factors, cytokines, tumour promoters, carcinogens, and oncogenes such as src and ras [61].

The activity of AP-1 is regulated by redox through the conserved cysteine residues that are located in the DNA-binding domain of each sub-unit protein [27,44]. Replacement of these cysteine residues by serine increases the DNA-binding activity. Furthermore, this type of mutation has been found in the naturally occurring oncogene v-jun [62]. In addition, mutation of Cys-154 to serine in Fos enhances its transforming activity by increasing the DNA-binding activity [44], linking the redox regulation of AP-1 to tumorigenesis. Phosphorylation of Ser-73 and Ser-63 residues in c-Jun, and Thr-232 in c-Fos, within the transactivation domains also enhance transcriptional activity [63].

Tumour suppressor p53

The most well-characterised post-translational modification for tumour suppressor p53 is lysine methylation, which can bring about a number of functional changes [64]. However, p53 also has an exquisitely interesting and complex redox regulation process involving the modulation of several cysteine residues with the most important being Cys-173, Cys-235 and Cys-239 in the DNA-binding domain, which together with His-179 co-ordination of a divalent zinc atom [42].

When the above mentioned cysteine residues are oxidised, the DNA-binding activity of p53 is inhibited [65]. Such modulation is important for p53 participation in the induction of cell cycle arrest or apoptosis [66] so this has important implications for carcinogenesis. Ref-1 has been shown to be a

key controller of p53 activity through both redox-dependent and -independent mechanisms [67,68].

Moreover, the DNA-binding domain of p53 also contains four other conserved cysteines. Cys-275 and Cys-277 form a C-X-C motif located within a loop that binds in the major groove of DNA. Cys-277 is exposed at the protein surface and donates a hydrogen bond to bases in the major groove of DNA, playing a role in the redox regulation of DNA binding in vitro [42].

Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF1 α)

HIF1 α has a basic-helix-loop-helix (bHLH)-PAS (conserved region among Per, Arnt and Sim) domain at the N-terminal and two transcription activation domains which are inducible in response to hypoxia and are localised in the C-terminal half, called NAD (N-terminal activation domain) and CAD (C-terminal activation domain). Hypoxia-inducible genes such as erythropoietin (Epo), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) and glycolytic enzymes are activated through binding of HIF1 α to the asymmetric Ebox-like element (HRE), having the core sequence TACGTG, in response to a low oxygen concentration [45].

The CAD domain of HIF1 α includes a redox-sensitive cysteine residue, Cys-800, which is essential for hypoxia-inducible interaction with the N-terminal region of CREB binding protein (CBP/p300) and therefore transactivation activity under hypoxic conditions. It has been proposed that Ref-1 and Txn act upon Cys-800 to form a free sulfhydryl group essential for the interaction with CBP and important for transcriptional activation. On the other hand, the NAD has no redox-sensitive cysteine residues and presents a different mechanism by which it interacts with CBP/p300, whereby the interaction is mediated by an additional factor [45].

Polyoma virus enhancer-binding protein 2 (PEBP2)

PEBP2 is a heterodimeric transcription factor composed of an α sub-unit which has a Runt domain responsible for both DNA-binding with the consensus sequence RACCRCA and heterodimerisation, and a β sub-unit which regulates the DNA-binding activity of the α sub-unit through allosteric interactions. The Runt domain of the α sub-unit contains two redox-sensitive cysteine residues, Cys-115 and Cys-124, affecting DNA-binding activity [48].

Cys-115 and Cys-124 were shown to undergo independent redox regulation, with Cys-115 being much less sensitive to oxidising agents than Cys-124. Cys-124 is highly liable to oxidation because of the flanking basic amino acids, leading to a strong reduction in DNA-binding activity, while on the other hand, Cys-115 has no neighbouring basic amino acids, resulting in a lower redox sensitivity. This independence enables more flexible regulation of DNA-binding activity in response to diverse cellular redox signals [48].

Moreover, the β sub-unit allosterically enhances the intrinsic DNA-binding affinity and acts as a modulator of redox-sensitivity of the Runt domain by protecting Cys-115 and Cys-124 from oxidation, possibly via alterations to the local environment of these cysteines in terms of their spatial alignment with neighboring charged amino acids or their involvement in intra- or inter-molecular hydrogen bonding. It has also been determined that the activity of the β sub-unit is further enhanced by Txn and Ref-1 [48].

cAMP-responsive element-binding protein (CREB)

CREB derives its name from its ability to bind to the consensus sequence TGACGTC, known as the cAMP-responsive element (CRE). At the C-terminal, CREB has a basic leucine zipper (bZIP), which is composed of leucine repeats involved in dimerisation and a basic helix region which is required for DNA-interaction, while the transactivation domain is contained within the kinase-inducible domain (KID) at the N-terminal. Several hypoxia-inducible genes contain CREs, such as lactate dehydrogenase A (LDH-A), tyrosine hydroxylase (TH), erythropoietin (Epo), and Ref-1 and are known to be regulated by CREB [49].

Two cysteine residues, Cys-300 and Cys-310, located in the DNA-binding portion of the bZIP domain of CREB can be reduced to increase the efficiency of binding of CREB to its CRE binding site in an additive manner. The substitution of these two cysteine residues by serine results in a loss of the redox-related response and in an increased activation of CRE-mediated gene expression in normoxia, up to the level of activation reached by wild-type CREB in hypoxia [49].

Heat Shock Factor 1 (HSF1)

HSF1 is the major transcription factor required for the expression of HSPs, in response to various forms of stress. This transcription factor contains a DNA binding-domain at the N-terminal, a regulatory domain in the mid-region and a transactivation domain at the C-terminal. HSF1 is found as monomer in the cytoplasm and upon stress induction, it undergoes homo-trimerisation via the C-terminus, which leads to translocation into the nucleus, activation of DNA-binding affinity to the heat shock element (HSE), transactivation as well as phosphorylation, resulting in protection of cells from stress-induced apoptosis [50,51].

There are two conflicting views of how this activation takes place. The first mechanism reported was that cysteine residues Cys-36 or Cys-103 (within the DNA-binding and adjacent linker domain respectively) have no effect on the redox-sensitivity of HSF1, while Cys-153 (in the regulatory domain) can form an intramolecular disulfide cross-link with either Cys-373 or Cys-378 (in the transactivation domain) and in so doing inhibit homo-trimerisation and hence

activation of HSF1 [50]. The second mechanism reported was that Cys-153 has no effect on HSF1 activation and instead cysteine residues Cys-36, Cys-103 are required to form or stabilise homo-trimerisation of HSF1 and subsequent processes [51].

Nuclear Factor I/ CCAAT Transcription Factor (NFI/CTF)

The NFI transcription factor is encoded by four different genes that can form homo- and heterodimers. They are characterised by a N-terminus which contains the DNA-binding domain and is also required for dimerisation, while the C-terminus is composed of a proline-rich region constituting the transcription-activating domain. The DNA-binding domain of NFI recognises a consensus sequence composed of one (GCCA) or two (TCCGN and GCCA) sequence elements [46].

Contrary to the other transcription factors described in this section, which have redox-sensitive cysteines in the DNA-binding domain, in NFI, the redox sensitive cysteine, Cys-427, is found in the transactivation domain, meaning that the activity of NFI is repressed by oxidative stress through a transactivating function. NFI can be activated by transforming growth factor β (TGF β) or repressed by tumour necrosis factor α (TNF α) and oxidative stress. It has been shown that Cys-427 (but not Cys-405) in the transactivation domain is indispensable for the repressive effect by H₂O₂ and the oxidation of Cys-427 is hypothesised to affect the conformation of the transactivation domain and disrupt protein-protein interactions required for the activation of transcription [46].

Nuclear transcription factor Y (NF-Y)

NF-Y is a hetero-trimeric transcription factor composed of NF-YA, NF-YB, and NF-YC sub-units that specifically recognises the CCAAT box motif. Each sub-unit in the NF-Y complex is functionally unique. While the NF-YA and NF-YC appear to contain structurally similar DNA-binding, sub-unit association, and transactivation domains, their protein-protein interactions have different requirements and while NF-YC can directly interact with NF-YB, NF-YA is not capable of binding either NF-YB or NF-YC individually. Conversely, NF-YB contains no transactivation domain but houses two essential redox sensitive cysteines, Cys-85 and Cys-89, in its DNA-binding domain. The NF-Y hetero-trimer requires the reduction of these two cysteines (probably via Ref-1) to efficiently bind the CCAAT box DNA motif as well as for sub-unit association of NF-YB with NF-YC [47].

NF-YB can form either inter- or intra-molecular (with another NF-YB sub-unit) disulfide cross-links resulting in a failure to interact with NF-YC, and this gives rise to a significant loss of DNA-binding activity. It has been suggested that the formation of an intra-molecular disulfide cross-link

and DNA-binding ability, thereby altering signalling pathways, through its response to oxidative stress, makes it a very interesting and powerful potential preventive and therapeutic target. Furthermore, synergistic or competitive effects with other redox-sensitive cysteines within the same protein or within different sub-units adds to the complexity and refinement of such regulation. Understanding such redox-regulated mechanisms will greatly contribute towards better preventive and therapeutic care against cancer.

Perspectives

Ongoing research focusing on the cysteine redox-regulation of E4TF1-60 is currently focusing on Cys-338, Cys-388, Cys-401 and Cys-421 to elucidate which cysteine residues specifically alter the DNA-binding affinity of this transcription factor, both by direct attachment to the DNA-motif and its stability by binding E4TF1-47/53. This does not exclude the possibility that other cysteines might assist in the protein's function. Also being considered is the cancer-context in which such a modification occurs, to better link the biochemical stimulus to the clinical consequences of this post-translational modification.

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